

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY OF 2,4-DINITROPHENYL AND 2,4,6-TRINITROPHENYL ETHERS OF VANILLIN SCHIFF'S BASES.

S. No.	R ₁	M.P. °C	Molecular* Formula	Diameter** of zones of inhibition in mm. for pathogenic fungi at Concentrations** (percent, W/V)											
				<i>Alternaria alternata</i>				<i>Drechslera papendorfi</i>				<i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i>			
				2	0.2	0.02	0.002	2	0.2	0.02	0.002	2	0.2	0.02	0.002
R=2,4-DINITROPHENYL															
1.	H	86	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₆	38	21	—	—	38	27	—	—	25	19	—	—
2.	Cl	88-9	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₆	45	28	—	—	46	35	24	—	44	30	17	—
3.	Br	90	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₆	43	27.5	—	—	58	40	30	—	45	33	16	—
4.	I	89	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ IN ₂ O ₆	44	35	—	—	63	52	33	24	52	38	18	15
5.	CH ₃	85	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₆	53	40	14	—	41	37	—	—	38	30	25	—
6.	OCH ₃	84	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₇	52	40	—	—	43	34	29	—	40	32	28	22
7.	NO ₂	149-50	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₈	48	29	22	15	53	43	26	16	42	28	16	—
R=2,4,6-TRINITROPHENYL															
8.	H	179	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₈	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
9.	Cl	173-74	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ClN ₄ O ₈	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
10.	Br	186	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ BrN ₄ O ₈	22	17	14	—	24	22	18	—	22	18	14.5	—
11.	I	183	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ IN ₄ O ₈	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
12.	CH ₃	163	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₈	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
13.	OCH ₃	174	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₉	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
14.	NO ₂	145-46	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₁₀	36	28	16	—	51	34	26	—	35	27	16	—
*§ Thiram 75 w				40	28	—	—	40	32	25	—	36	28	14	—

* Analysis for C, H and N was performed and found within the range ±0.4%. The yield ranged from 47-52%.

(-) Shows no zone of inhibition.

** Three replicates averaged.

*‡ These concentrations were prepared by dissolving the compounds in dioxan.

*§ Used as a reference fungicide.

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